

Table 2. Calculation of the number of tablespoons of liquid insecticides to add to your sprayer each sprayerload to achieve a dosage of 0.75 kg active ingredient/ha. IRRI.

Sprayerloads (no./ha) ^a	Number of tablespoons per sprayerload of liquid insecticides when insecticide concentration (% a.i.) on the bottle is											
	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70
10	50	38	30	25	21	19	17	15	14	13	12	11
15	33	25	20	17	14	13	11	10	9	8	8	7
20	25	19	15	13	11	9	8	8	7	6	6	5
25	20	15	12	10	9	8	7	6	5	5	5	4
30	17	13	10	8	7	6	6	5	5	4	4	4
35	14	11	9	7	6	5	5	4	4	4	3	3
40	13	9	8	6	5	5	4	4	3	3	3	3
45	11	8	7	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	3	2
50	10	8	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	3	2	2
55	9	7	5	5	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
60	8	6	5	4	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
65	8	6	5	4	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
70	7	5	4	4	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2

^aFrom Table 1.

Table 3. Calculation of the number of tablespoons of wettable powders to add to your sprayer each sprayerload to achieve a dosage of 0.75 kg a.i./ha. IRRI.^a

Sprayerloads (no./ha)	Number of tablespoons of WP per sprayerload				
	Etofolan Mipcin Hytox MIPC 50 WP	Shellcarb BPMC 40 WP	Tsumacide MTMC 50 WP	Orthene 75 SP	Sevin Tercyl 85 WP
10	39	51	37	34	38
15	26	34	24	23	25
20	20	25	18	17	19
25	16	20	15	14	15
30	13	17	12	11	13
35	11	14	10	10	11
40	10	13	9	9	9
45	9	11	8	8	8
50	8	10	7	7	8
55	7	9	7	6	7
60	7	8	6	6	6
65	6	8	6	5	6
70	6	7	5	5	5
G/tablespoon	3.8	3.7	4.1	2.9	2.3

^aWP = wettable powder, SP = soluble powder.

column labeled 50 down to the row designated 35 sprayerloads/ha (33 rounds off to 35). The correct dosage then is 4 tablespoons/sprayerload. Note that a tablespoon = 10 ml.

Table 3 gives calculations for wettable powders. Wettable powders are calculated individually because the weight of one tablespoon of the formulated product varies among insecticides. For liquids we assumed that the weight of 1 liter of insecticide was equal to the weight of 1 liter of water. But wettable powders have different dispersing agents and carriers that have

different weights. If a recommended wettable powder insecticide is not in Table 3, use the following formula for 0.75 kg. a.i./ha dosage to calculate the appropriate data in tablespoons for 10-70 sprayerloads/ha:

$$\text{No. of tablespoons} = 750 \times \frac{100}{\text{concentration of product}} \times \frac{1}{\text{sprayerloads (no./ha)}} \times \frac{1}{\text{g/l tablespoon (10 cc) of product}}$$

Note that you need to know the weight of 1 tablespoon of the formulated product.

Observations on a “blue form” of green leafhopper

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In January 1980 a few colored insects, resembling green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* were noticed in the insect maintenance cages at AICRIP headquarters, Hyderabad. Twenty-five such insects, both males and females, were caged on TN1 seedlings. Eight days later the first-instar nymphs appeared and molted within 2-3 days. After that the second-instar nymphs were clearly distinguishable from those of “normal” green leafhopper nymphs. Later generations showed that the blue forms bred true and that the blue and green forms can crossbreed. To determine if the two forms differ in the ability to transmit tungro virus disease, males and females of both forms were released on tungro-infected TN1 plants for 24 hours. Transmission tests showed that as transmitters of rice tungro virus the blue females were as efficient as the green, but the green males were better than the blue. Further work is in progress and the insects have been sent to the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology for identification. ■

The “knockdown speed” of insecticides against brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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The “knockdown action” of some commonly used pesticides for the control of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Dist.) was studied.

Single hills (5 plants each) of 25-day-old rice plants were transplanted in plastic pots (3 inches in diameter). Desired concentrations of insecticides were sprayed on the potted plants on a